

Neighbourhood analysis of pure and mixed Sal forests at Madhupur, Bangladesh

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The Madhupur Sal forests play a vital role in the people's livelihood and are of significant importance in maintaining the biodiversity of the middle portions of Bangladesh's ecosystems. Besides the importance of vertical and horizontal structures for biodiversity-related aspects, structural diversity is a matter of concern within forest management. The aggregation of tree species is essential for space and growing conditions for each individual. The applicability of indicators to assess the structural diversity of Sal forests has not been evaluated at present. Therefore, a study was undertaken to assess mixed and pure Sal forests' structural diversity at Madhupur by some diversity indicators developed for species-poor systems in Europe. Based on 60 sample plots, an analysis of 173 sample trees and related 692 neighbours were done. Species mingling, diameter and height dominance, uniform angle index and diameter, and height differentiation were calculated. The results indicated that within the mixed Sal forests, 40% of the trees were Sal, and within the pure forests, 95% of the trees were Sal. The uniform angle index in mixed and pure Sal forests was 0.61 and 0.34, respectively, which indicated a tendency towards clumped dispersion of trees in pure and regular dispersion of trees in mixed Sal forests. The results revealed that diameter dominance was random in mixed and regular in pure Sal forests, but height dominance was regular in both forests. Diameter and height differentiation were smaller in pure forests than mixed forests. The mean distance from a sample tree to the first, second, third, and fourth neighbour indicated that pure Sal forests were more densely populated than mixed Sal forests. It was found that indicators supporting neighbourhood analysis can be effectively used as a simple, easy, and quick method for estimating the spatial diversity of the Sal forest of Bangladesh. The use of these techniques and the combination of different indices supports an integrative assessment of these forest ecosystems, leading to a better evaluation of management practices for naturalness, ecosystem stability, or sustainability.